

Marketing Mix Analysis of Repurchase Intention with Variable of Mediation Purchase Decision of Parents of Sd Strada Students In Jakarta

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Abstract:- Basic education service is a line of business that can bind customers in the long term. Purchasing decisions are influenced by several considerations of marketing mix variables, namely product, price, promotion and place. The long duration of consumption for basic education services can determine the intention to repurchase the services. This study aims to analyse the effect of the marketing mix on repurchase intentions, by looking at the decision to choose a school as a mediation. The population was taken from parents of new grade students who entered the 2021/2022 academic year, with as many as 828 people, 270 samples were derived and spread proportionally to 17 schools based on the number of the students. The data was processed using the SEM method with the tool of SMART-PLS software. The four variables also have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions with a size effect of product (0.235), price

(0.145), promotion (0.928) and place (0.141). Purchase decision has a positive and significant effect as a mediating variable among the four marketing mix variables with repurchase intentions.

Keywords:- Product, Price, Promotion, Place, Purchase Decision, Repurchase Intention.

I. INTRODUCTION

Elementary school, is a level of education that really needs parental consideration. This happens because this level has a big influence on the next level of education in the future (Afridayani & Muarif, 2020). The growing number of primary schools in Jakarta means that there are more options for parents as well as increased competition among old and new schools.

Table 1. Data on Private Elementary Schools in DKI Jakarta

School Year	Number of Schools	Number of Pupils	Average number of pupils per school
2016/2017	923	236965	684
2017/2018	1008	249200	696
2018/2019	963	248222	715
2019/2020	975	250073	724
2020/2021	1171	242800	671

Source: <https://jakarta.bps.go.id>, 2021.

Basic education service products focus on education and character development. Primary school teachers play an important role in providing a foundation for children. The quality of teacher services in teaching and educating is very important so that children who are students can succeed until their graduation (Ayolugbe, Ishiwu, & Ugodinamba, 2019). Mastery of teaching materials in accordance with appropriate knowledge and literacy needs to be developed by teachers in accordance with the concrete operational context that is the development period of children of primary school age.

Tuition fees are an important and powerful factor for parents to consider. Figure 1 shows that school participation rates are getting higher as the economy improves. Private school fees paid by customers become a source of expenditure for school operations so that the number of students received will be directly proportional to the income required as such operational expenses.

This experience and information becomes knowledge that is used as one of the guidelines for consumers to choose products and services, including in the field of education. Potential customers find their knowledge of the school that is sought after from various sources such as information from friends and family as well as social media and the internet. In modern times, any information is very easy to search for and very quickly circulates especially if the information is not good. The management of Strada school pays special attention in carrying out this kind of promotional activities so that it is better known and can be used as the choice of potential customers. School promotion activities are a new but increasingly concerned matter for private schools these days (Dâmasoa & Lima, 2019; Kohout-Diaz, 2018; Turner, 2017; McDonald, Pini, & Bartlett, 2019; Mazurek, Korzyński, & Górska, 2019; Lee, 2019). The geographical base is the most widely used market segmentation strategy by private education providers to increase pupil count and financial gains (Mandal & Swamy, 2020; Chami & Yakhne, 2018).

Table 2. Pre-Survey Results of Parents of Grade 1 Students of SD Strada in Jakarta

Driving factors	Amount	%
The child's knowledge, skills and/or character are well developed	25	83%
The extracurricular activities are good and interesting	7	23%
Willing to accept children with a younger age than public schools	6	20%
Learning by teachers is interesting and fun	11	37%
The facilities and infrastructure are complete	10	33%
Strada schools are famous everywhere	8	27%
Cost according to financial capabilities	27	90%
Not expensive when compared to other schools	6	20%
Transparent Tuition Management for child development	10	33%
Information about the school is easy to find on social media and the internet	21	70%
There are scholarships of underprivileged students and outstanding students	10	33%
There are many interesting activities outside the lesson such as the environment, competitions, appearances, etc.	15	50%
Many interesting activities outside the lesson such as the environment	14	47%
Social media is active and interactive towards its visitors	4	13%
It is located close by, easy to reach from everywhere	23	77%
The Strada School has many branches everywhere	11	37%
Has a parking lot and a large yard	7	23%
The place is very supportive to learn because it is a lot of plants and cool	19	63%

Source: Researcher's pre-survey results, 2022

Table 2 above shows that the most interested factor is about tuition fees that are considered to be in accordance with the financial capabilities of parents selected by 90% of respondents. The second factor is that 83% of respondents are interested because the educational outcomes at Strada Elementary School can make children's knowledge, skills and character develop properly. The relatively close and easy-to-reach location of the school from everywhere also contributed as a factor that became the interest of parents in 3rd place with as many as 77% of parents. Meanwhile, 21 parents (70%) expressed interest in stating that information about the school is easy to find on social media or the internet. The top four factors that reached 70% of the pre-research results are considered quite significant and can represent the variable marketing mix consisting of products in the form of educational services, prices in the form of tuition fees for the duration at the elementary level, promotions and places.

Based on the background outlined above, the study sets the following objectives:

1. To find out and analyze the influence of product, price, promotion and place on the repurchase intention of parents.
2. To find out and analyze the influence of product, price, promotion and place on the purchase decision to choose a school.
3. To find out and analyze the effect of the purchase decision to choose a school on the repurchase intention of parents.
4. To find out and analyze the influence of marketing mix with mediation of the purchase decision on the repurchase intention.

II. THEORETICAL STUDIES

➤ *Repurchase Intention*

Balla in Hudaya (2020) explained that repurchase intention in terms of products in the form of service services is an assessment from customers about the purchase of these services from the same company after going through consideration of the situation or circumstances. Meanwhile, when viewed from a behavioral point of view, the intention of the repurchase is the possibility of the customer to declare that he is involved in the repurchase in the future. Collier and Bienstock in Hudaya (2020) said that the intention of repurchase is in addition to the customer's willingness to return to purchase service products, but can be in the form of an intention to provide recommendations on the service product to their colleagues and relatives. Harris and Goode in Adekunle (2018) describe repurchase intentions related to the choice of a particular brand of service product to a similar need present in the future. The repurchase intention is a commitment from customers to be firm in supporting an offer in the form of a product or service (Xu and Liu in Adenkule, 2018).

➤ *Purchase Decision*

Decision making by the customer is an integrated process by combining several knowledge to evaluate two or more alternative behaviors and choose one of them (Kotler, Keller, Brady, Goodman, & Hansen, 2009). The decision-making process tends to maximize or have full satisfaction with the decisions made. The process represents the individual's self-satisfaction that no matter what the decision is, right or wrong, the consumer will do all the necessary research before making a decision (Chami & Yakhne, 2018). Kotler and Gary (2012) explain that the purchase decision

process consists of 5 stages, namely: (1) recognition of needs, (2) search for information, (3) evaluation of alternatives, (4) purchase decisions, and (5) post-purchase behavior.

➤ *Product*

Broadly speaking, a product constitutes everything that can be offered to the market to satisfy a desire or need and consists of a set of attributes, including physical goods, services, experiences, events, people, places, property, organizations, information, and ideas (Kotler et al., 2009; Armstrong, Kotler, Trifts, Buchwitz, & Gaudet, 2017; Kotler & Armstrong, 2012). In the products of goods consumed, there are services that are used and obtained to satisfy the desires of consumers. Vice versa, in the service products sold, there are tangible goods that can be obtained as a physical form that can meet consumer needs. Products in the form of services as a selling point have characteristics that are not the same when juxtaposed with products in the form of goods. Zeithmal & Bitner in Chaston (2017) explains the inherent relative differences of service products to goods as follows: (1) intangibility, that is, they cannot be seen, tasted or touched; (2) heterogeneity, i.e. the possibility of variation in perceived service; (3) perishability, that is, the nature of the service that cannot be saved for subsequent sales; and (4) simultaneously in production and consumption, that is, the services produced can only be used on the spot by the customer. Armstrong et al. (2017) classify products into three product levels as shown in figure 2, namely: (1) core customer value, (2) actual product, and (3) augmented product. Core value is a core benefit received through a series of experiences of buying or using an actual product. While the augmented product is an additional service that accompanies the actual product.

Armstrong et al. (2017) divide *actual product* into 5 namely:

- a) Feature, namely the special characteristics contained in the barang or service. In the field of basic education services, it is related for example to the teaching and learning process, curriculum and applicable laws and regulations.
- b) Design, which is a framework of form, design in conveying abrang or services to customers. For educational services, the design can be both a fun learning approach and character education.
- c) Packaging, which is packaging or containers where the product is shipped. This can be related to buildings and infrastructure owned by schools as a forum for services provided.
- d) Quality level, that is, the quality levels. For educational service products, the quality is highly dependent on the teacher who is the person who is directly in charge of delivering the educational services to the students who are customers.
- e) Brand image, that is, the visual or verbal expression of a brand that leads to psychological or emotional associations that the brand wants to maintain in the minds of consumers Kotler et al.(2009).

➤ *Price*

The amount of money determined to get a product of goods or services. Price is also the amount of value exchanged by the customer for benefits, owning or using a product or service (Kotler & Armstrong, 2012; Kotler et al., 2017; Tomczak, 2018), a figure set as a substitute for the cost and target profit to be achieved. Because only subjectively perceived price is an important factor in purchasing decisions, and there is often a considerable difference between perception and objective price levels (Tomczak et al., 2018). Diller (2008) states that companies should make decisions for various components of the product and customer groups regarding the extent to which the following pricing objectives are pursued (Tomczak et al., 2018): (1) affordability, (2) value for money, (3) trust and fairness of prices, and (4) price satisfaction.

➤ *Promotion*

The flow of information or one-way persuasion to direct a person or organization towards actions that create exchanges in marketing (Swastha & Irawan, 2005). According to Kotler et al., (2012) promotion means an activity that communicates the benefits of a product and persuades target customers to buy it. . If schools create more means of communication, they will be tied to the external environment to promote the school's goals, mission, vision, and values to learners and their parents (Chami & Yakhne, 2018). Modern marketing communication media for promotion using a blend of new and traditional media (Tomczak et al., 2018). Armstrong et al. , (2017) explained that there are 5 aspects in promotional activities, namely advertising, sales si sales, personal sales, public relations, direct / digital marketing.

➤ *Place*

What is meant by place in the marketing mix is the distribution channel (Kotler et al., 2009; Tomczak et al., 2018). A distribution channel is a set of interdependent units that help make a product or service available for use or consumption by consumers or business customers (Armstrong et al., 2017). Distribution channels are dynamic. They can create a competitive advantage when used correctly, but become a competitive obligation when used poorly (Kotler, 2003). Hastings et al. in Chami and Yakhne (2018) stated that the location of the school is one of the choices of parents before choosing a school. According to Tomczak et al. (2018) there are regions, channels, branches/members and logistics.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

➤ *Frame of Mind*

This research uses quantitative and descriptive / explanatory causal research methods because the problems that are the starting point of the research are clear (Sugiyono, 2014). The variables used in the study consist of independent variables that affect or are the cause of changes in dependent variables, and moderator variables that strengthen or weaken the relationship between independent and dependent variables (Rachbini, Rachbini, Santoso, Prayitno & Khumaedi, 2020).

Based on the theory of repurchase intention (Z) by Gounaris et al., in Pather (2017) and Collier and Bienstock in Hudaya (2020) there are 2 dimensi namely the intention to buy back and the intention in recommending products of goods / services.

Based on the theory of the decision to choose (Y) by Kotler and Armstrong (2020) there are 3 stages that are used as dimensions in this study , namely the introduction of needs, the search for information and the evaluation of alternatives.

Based on the theory about the product (X₁) by Armstrong et al., (2017) at the actual product level, there are

5 dimensions used, namely *feature, design, packaging, quality, and brand image.*

Based on the theory of price (X₂) by Tomczak (2018) there are 3 dimensions used for this study, namely affordability, value of money and trust / fairness of prices.

Based on the theory of promotion (X₃) by Kotler et al., (2012) there are 3 dimensions used in research, namely advertising, sales promotion and direct / digital marketing.

Based on the theory of place (X₄) by Tomczak (2018) there is 1 dimension used in research, namely about the area of operational coverage.

Fig 2. Frame of Mind

➤ *Research Hypothesis*

From the research objectives above and the theoretical studies presented, the hypotheses obtained in this study are as follows.

H₁-H₄ Product, price, place and promotion have positive and significant effects on repurchase intention.

H₅-H₈ Product, price, place and promotion have positive and significant effects on purchase decision on choosing a school.

H₉ Purchase decision on choosing a school has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention.

H₁₀ Marketing mix with mediation purchase decision to choose a school has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention.

➤ *Population and Sample*

The object of the study was the parents of grade 1 students who sent their children to Strada Elementary School which is located throughout the Jakarta area. The total number of schools is 13 elementary schools with the number of grade 1 students when this study was conducted, which was 828 people as a population. The number of samples used using the Slovin formula was 270 people, which was divided proportionally based on the ratio of the number of students of 13 elementary schools. Data collection from respondents was carried out using the questionnaire method with a total of 20 surveys using a 5-level likert scale.

➤ *Test Instruments*

The testing of the research instrument is aimed at assessing the validity and reliability of the instrument. Validity testers in this study used Pearson Bivariate correlation (Pearson Moment Products). All 20 items of survey questions are more than 0.361 and declared valid. Reliability testing measuring the nature of measurements of a

test by subjects under the same conditions can result in consistently similar or similar measurements after repeated attempts. Testing the reliability of the instrument using the Alpha Cronbach formula, obtained a value of 0.946, which is more than 0.70 so that it can be concluded that the entire survey question item has a strong reliability.

Table 3. Outer Measurement Model Test Results

Indicator	Loading Factor	Cronbach's Alpha	CR	AVE
Product		0.913	0.929	0.724
Strada School has good and satisfying extracurricular activities	0.784			
Learning at the Strada school is interesting and fun for the child	0.901			
Buildings, facilities and infrastructure in the Strada school are complete	0.774			
Strada School has teachers who are of good quality in teaching	0.893			
Strada school is able to develop children's knowledge and skills well	0.892			
Price		0.791	0.875	0.701
Tuition fees in Strada are still affordable with the income I/we have	0.802			
Tuition fees in Strada are not expensive compared to other schools	0.852			
The tuition fees paid are beneficial for education and teaching	0.857			
Promotion		0.701	0.834	0.626
Information about the Strada school is easy to find in various sources	0.762			
Strada school provides discounted/tuition fees or payment waivers	0.826			
Strada School is active and interactive on social media	0.785			
Place		0.767	0.863	0.678
The location of the Strada school is relatively close to where it lives	0.788			
The location of the Strada school is easily accessible to various means of private transportation and public transportation	0.845			
Strada has many elementary schools spread throughout the Jakarta area	0.836			
Repurchase Intention		0.857	0.913	0.778
If anything, I would like to enroll my child or relatives into Strada school	0.870			
I am willing to recommend to my relationship to send their children to school in Strada	0.914			
I am willing to make recommendations on my social media for Strada school	0.860			
The purchase decision to choose		0.707	0.837	0.631
I chose Strada School because it suits my needs	0.816			
I chose the Strada school because it has enough information	0.783			
I chose Strada school after comparing with various other school options	0.783			

Source: Research data processing results, 2022

➤ *Test Data Analysis*

Data analysis testing using the SEM PLS model. The first SEM PLS model measurement in the outer model is a reflective measurement that includes composite reliability, individual indicator reliability, and average variance extract (AVE) to evaluate convergent validity, as well as Fornell-Larcker criteria and cross loading used to assess the validity of discriminants. The results can be seen in table 3. The overall survey and variable items are above the lower threshold. Composite reliability, Cronbach's Alpha and outer loading of more than 0.70 and AVE values of more than 0.50 indicate that the research data have good construct reliability.

Table 4. Fornell-Locker criteria

	Product	Price	Promotion	Place	Decision to Choose	Repurchase Intention
Product	0.851					
Price	0.623	0.837				
Promotion	0.434	0.297	0.791			
Place	0.595	0.617	0.345	0.823		
Purchase Decision to Choose	0.679	0.584	0.442	0.556	0.882	
Repurchase Intention	0.703	0.609	0.599	0.608	0.697	0.794

Source: Research data processing results, 2022

The Fornell-Locker criteria in table 4 above show the value of each variable is higher in its construct compared to other constructs.

Table 5. Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio

	Product	Price	Promotion	Place	Purchase Decision to Choose	Repurchase Intention
Product						
Price	0.698					
Promotion	0.546	0.381				
Place	0.696	0.770	0.461			
Purchase Decision to Choose	0.760	0.687	0.567	0.660		
Repurchase Intention	0.878	0.787	0.850	0.809	0.890	

Source: Research data processing results, 2022

The HTMT Ratio value in the study is shown in table 5. In the table, it can be seen that the entire HTMT Ratio value is below the number 0.9 so it can be ascertained that the validity of the discriminant between the two reflective constructs.

Table 6. Cholinearity Test Results

Variable	BRIGHT
Product (X₁)	
Strada School has good and satisfying extracurricular activities	1.926
Learning at the Strada school is interesting and fun for the child	3.257
Buildings, facilities and infrastructure in the Strada school are complete	1.877
Strada School has teachers who are of good quality in teaching	3.571
Strada school is able to develop children's knowledge and skills well	3.607
Price (X₂)	
Tuition fees in Strada are still affordable with the income I/we have	1.744
Tuition fees in Strada are not expensive compared to other schools	1.964
The tuition fees paid are beneficial for education and teaching	1.513
Promotion (X₃)	
Information about the Strada school is easy to find in various sources	1.320
Strada school provides discounted/tuition fees or payment waivers	1.489
Strada School is active and interactive on social media	1.351
Place (X₄)	
The location of the Strada school is relatively close to where it lives	1.638
The location of the Strada school is easily accessible to various means of private transportation and public transportation	1.886
Strada has many elementary schools spread throughout the Jakarta area	1.426
Purchase Decision to Choose (Y)	
If anything, I would like to enroll my child or relatives into Strada school	2.119
I am willing to recommend to my relationship to send their children to school in Strada	2.453
I am willing to make recommendations on my social media for Strada school	2.012
Repurchase Intention (Z)	
I chose Strada School because it suits my needs	1.462
I chose the Strada school because it has enough information	1.340

I chose Strada school after comparing with various other school options	1.367
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Source: Research data processing results, 2022

For the structural model test (inner model) the first is the evaluation of collinearity. In table 6 it can be seen that the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value of all survey instruments of each variable is less than 5. Thus it can be concluded that the entire indicator of the variable is not subjected to collinearity.

Table 7. Estimated Significance

	Direct effects	t value		Indirect effects	t value	Total effects	t value
X ₁ -> Y	0.404	6.376				0.404	6.376
X ₁ -> Z	0.235	3.621	X ₁ -> Y -> Z	0.098	3.192	0.333	5.692
X ₂ -> Y	0.201	2.989				0.201	2.989
X ₂ -> Z	0.145	2.928	X ₂ -> Y -> Z	0.048	2.315	0.194	3.685
X ₃ -> Y	0.160	3.046				0.160	3.046
X ₃ -> Z	0.298	7.311	X ₃ -> Y -> Z	0.039	2.196	0.337	8.163
X ₄ -> Y	0.137	1.982				0.137	1.982
X ₄ -> Z	0.141	2.569	X ₄ -> Y -> Z	0.033	1.966	0.174	3.012
Y -> Z	0.242	4.007				0.242	4.007

Source: Research data processing results, 2022

The significance test in table 7 shows that the entire path has a t value of more than 1.96 so that all paths are significant and acceptable in this study.

From the results of data analysis, it was obtained that products, prices, promotions and places had a positive and significant effect on the interest in repurchase, with each of them having a large influence for each unit of product unit (23.5%) , price (14.5%), promotion (29.8%) and place (14.1%). Thus H₁, H₂, H₃ and H₄ are accepted. Likewise, the four variables of the marketing mix have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions, with the magnitude of the influence of each unit of product unit (40.4%), price (20.1%), promotion (16.0%) and place (13.7%). Thus H₅, H₆, H₇ and H₈ are accepted. The results of the analysis also showed a positive and significant influence between the purchase decision and the repurchase intention with a large influence of 13.7% for each unit unit, which means that H₉ is received. On the indirect relationship between the marketing mix and the repurchase interest mediated by the purchase decision, each mix variable has a positive and significant effect on the repurchase interest mediated by the purchase decision. The magnitude of this indirect relationship is for each variable of product (9.8%), price (4.8%), promotion (3.9%) and place (3.9%). Thus H₁₀ is acceptable.

IV. DISCUSSION

Customers should consider the educational service products they will use for at least 6 years at the Primary School level. Previous research explained the positive relationship between products and the decision to choose a school (Afridayani & Muarif, 2020; Rahman, 2017; Kurliyatin, Bafadal, & Zulkarnain, 2017; Rosha, Wati, & Dharma, 2017; Enjina, Samsuddin, & Kurniasari, 2019; Rahmawati, 2019; Azizah, Sutansi, & Untari, 2021; Irawan, 2017; Sa'baniah, 2018). Evaluation of the product can encourage customers to determine their intention to repurchase the product or recommend it to others (Hudaya,

2020; Pather, 2017; Sullivan & Kim, 2017). This is a form of satisfaction with products that have been or are being used by customers (Pandiangan et al., 2021; Alafityanto & Djumarno, 2017; Fitriajaya & Nurmahdi, 2019).

The interview process for a price deal is an effective strategy. Consumers will feel the impact of the price agreement reached in the interview process during the continuity of the educational services they purchased. The right price agreement can positively affect buying intentions (Sutama & Hasthanti, 2018). For consumers who have decided on their purchase, the price aspect is a consideration for the interest in repurchase a product or service (Sullivan & Kim, 2017; Alafityanto & Djumarno, 2017). Hasil from several previous studies confirms the relationship between prices and consumers' decisions to choose products (Afridayani & Muarif, 2020; Rosha et al., 2017; Rahmawati, 2019; Azizah et al., 2021; Irawan, 2017; Sa'baniah, 2018).

The creativity of educators and education staff in utilizing each promotional path makes the influence of promotion better. Content and other promotional activities such as competitions can attract potential customers to then decide to choose a Strada school. Several previous studies have concluded that there is a relationship between promotion and school choice decisions (Afridayani & Muarif, 2020; Rosha et al., 2017; Rahmawati, 2019; Azizah et al., 2021; Irawan, 2017). The large number of social media users on the part of consumers has unwittingly played a role in expanding the network of information and communication about schools. Previous research suggesting a positive relationship between promotion and purchase interest (Munarsih, Akbar, & Sudarsono, 2020; Quintania et al., 2020; Siragi & Moses, 2018). Researchers see this can also happen with repurchase intention.

The existence of many scattered school branches convinces customers of the credibility of the school and becomes an opportunity for easy access if customers decide

to change residences. Ease of access using various modes of transportation is a consideration for customers. Thus the place factor becomes a factor that will influence customer decisions in making decisions to choose a school (Afridayani & Muarif, 2020; Rosha et al., 2017; Mohammed, 2021; Rahmawati, 2019; Azizah et al., 2021; Irawan, 2017; Sa'baniah, 2018; Djumarno, Ali, Sudrajat, & Lestari, 2020). Likewise, its influence on repurchase interest, in line with previous research which explains the relationship between place and buying interest (Muhammad, 2021; Sutama & Hasthanti, 2018).

The decisions made will be evaluated by the customer as a comparison between the expectations when the decision was made and the reality obtained. The experience gained generates perception, brand awareness and brand associations that ultimately affect the repurchase intention (Hudaya, 2020; Sudaryanto, Hanim, & Utari, 2020; Sullivan & Kim, 2017). Brand awareness and quality of service products will be affected by the service product itself which will ultimately determine the level of interest in repurchase services (Hudaya, 2020; Sudaryanto, Hanim, & Utari, 2020; Sullivan & Kim, 2017).

V. CONCLUSION

4P marketing policies in the form of product, price, promotion and place are variables that determine the success of schools in attracting customers. The decision to purchase educational services that are embodied in choosing a school for a child, is strongly influenced by the service product itself, the cost of schooling that must be incurred, price promotion, publication, sales and public relations, as well as the region where the school is located. Customers who decide to purchase educational services mean providing their commitments for purchases with a fairly long duration. During this long period, the evaluation of the services received both in terms of product, price, promotion and place, can trigger the repurchase intention realized through recommendations to others or make purchases of these educational services for their relatives. For schools, the purchase decision can be a mediation between the 4P marketing mix they managed from the beginning and the intention of repurchasing their educational services.

VI. SUGGESTION

It is important for any organization to maintain and improve the quality of the product. The right strategy in setting prices can benefit both parties, both customers and educational service providers. Schools need to further study promotional pathways to reach customers. Cooperation with policymakers and local communities can support schools. The long duration of purchasing educational services needs to be addressed with consistency in service quality, especially to customers who make purchasing decisions first.

For subsequent researchers, the marketing mix variable can be developed into 7Ps in order to be able to capture details that are not contained in the 4Ps mix. Data collection can be combined with interview techniques to obtain more accurate, complete and clear data. The development of research

models can be expanded or shifted to other levels of education such as junior high school or high school to see different processes in the customer realm.

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